

Data Management Plan

Data Analytics in WEKA Toolkit

Contact person: *There are no contact people define*

Based on: *Common DSW Knowledge Model, 2.0.1 (dsw:root:2.0.1)*

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Data Management Plan created in Data Stewardship Wizard <<https://ds-wizard.org>>

Abstract

In this experiment is shown the evaluation of the two classification algorithms: random forests and multilayer perceptron (MLP) on the example of an analysis of thyroid disease record dataset. Dataset consist of 3772 instances and 30 attributes. The data is preprocessed, and the mentioned algorithms are executed, in Weka Toolkit (Explorer).

Section A: Data Collection

1. What data will you collect or create?

Instrument datasets

The following instrument datasets will be acquired in the project:

- **Classification model and classifier errors**

This dataset will be collected by experts in the project, with our own equipment.

The equipment is very well described and known.

Re-used datasets

We will use the following reference datasets:

- **hypothyroid** (<https://www.openml.org/d/57>)

Data formats and types

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- **[CSV Dialect Description Format](#)**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 1 files of average size 0.0003 GB (i.e. approximately 0.0 GB in total).

2. How will the data be collected or created?

Instrument datasets

- **Classification model and classifier errors**

For this dataset, we are using the following instruments:

- **Weka Toolkit (Explorer)** – "Weka is tried and tested open source machine learning software that can be accessed through a graphical user interface, standard terminal applications, or a Java API." (<https://www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/ml/weka/>, last visited on 19.04.2020)

We will not be using quality process for this dataset.

Storage and file conventions

We will use a filesystem with files and folders with the following folder conventions:

- There will be a **folder for each sample/subject**. Each of those will use the following conventions: Specifying parameters and values used in the sample, e.g. default, trainingTime250.
- There will be a **(sub)folder for each (repeated) analysis**. Each of those will use the following conventions: Add version at the end of the folder e.g. _v1.

Moreover, we have made appointments about naming the files.

We will not be storing data in an "object store" system.

We will not use a relational database system to store project data.

We will not use a graph database for data in the project.

We will not be storing data in a triple store.

Section B: Documentation and Meta-data

3. What documentation and meta-data will accompany the data?

List of data to be published is given in Section E, Question 9. This also includes information about catalogs where the data can be found. Information about data types used is given in Section A, Question 1.

We will use other solution than (electronic) lab notebooks to make sure that there is good provenance of the data analysis: Using Wikis for tracking the steps.

Section C: Ethics and Legal Compliance

4. How will you manage any ethical issues?

5. How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

All of our data can become completely open immediately.

For the reference and non-reference data sets that we reuse, conditions are as follows:

- **hypothyroid** – freely available for any use (public domain or CC0).

Section D: Storage and Backup

6. How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

Data that project members themselves store adequately backed up and traceable. Therefore data are protected against both equipment failure and human error.

7. How will you manage access and security?

Project members will not store data or software on computers in the lab or external hard drives connected to those computers. All data centers where project data is stored carry sufficient certifications. All project web services addressed via secure http (<https://...>). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

The possible impact to the project or organization if information is lost is small. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is leaked is small. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is vandalised is small.

We are not using any personal information.

Section E: Selection and Preservation

8. Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

We plan to publish the following datasets:

- **models, parameters and errors** – This data set will be kept available as long as technically possible. – The metadata will be available even when the data no longer exists.

9. What is the longterm preservation plan for the dataset?

- **models, parameters and errors** will be stored in a special-purpose repository for the project. We will be able to support this repository for a sufficiently long time. The repository will provide download-only service.

None of the used repositories charge for their services.

Section F: Data Sharing

10. How will you share the data?

- **models, parameters and errors** – freely available for any use (public domain or CC0).

Information about used repositories (i.e. where will potential users find out about the data) is provided in Section E, Question 9.

Embargo on the data is described in Section C, Question 5, and Section F, Question 11.

11. Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Ethical and legal restrictions are documented under Section C. We have used the Data Stewardship Wizard, which made us aware of options to minimize the restrictions.

No data sharing agreement will be required.

Section G: Responsibilities and Resources

12. Who will be responsible for data management?

Mensur Besirovic is responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

13. What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

To execute the DMP, no additional specialist expertise is required.

We require the following hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in the institute: WEKA Toolkit (Explorer).

Charges applied by data repositories (if any) are mentioned already in Section E, Question 9.